

AN INTRODUCTION TO

PHYLOGENETICS

and its use in conservation biology

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INTRO

- I am a postdoc working on phylogeny and macroevolution
- 3D scanning of archosaurs (dinosaurs, birds, crocs) mostly!
- Mostly at Oxford now, but also at Museum für Naturkunde

Slides, handout, and further reading on website, Zenodo, and hopefully Moodle:

www.rsookias.info/teaching-resources

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3538047>

Do ask me any questions in class, or email me:
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INTRO

Overall plan:

1. Introduce the concept of phylogeny
2. Explain uses, especially in conservation
3. Introduce key terms and analytical methods, incl. practice exercise
4. Outline methods for application, esp. Conservation, and wider uses

Tonini et al. 2016 *Biol Conservation*

I think

Darwin 1837-8

WHAT IS PHYLOGENY?

Family tree of life

Species not individually created!

Phylogeny *is* evolution!

I think

Darwin 1837-8

WHY IS PHYLOGENY INTERESTING?

It's the history of life!

WHY IS PHYLOGENY INTERESTING?

Replaces traditional classification:
Linnaean system replaced with Hennigian clade-based system

WHY IS PHYLOGENY INTERESTING?

Helps ask wider questions, e.g.:

- Diversity patterns
- Mode and tempo of evolution
- Biogeography
- Timing of splits
- Effect of environment

Modified from Benton 2009 Science

WHY IS PHYLOGENY INTERESTING?

And *finally* ...it's useful in conservation! Loads of uses, incl.:

- Effect of environmental changes on diversity
- Pinpoint taxa at risk
- Pinpoint areas/species to prioritise
- Population genetics/distinctiveness

Modified from Benton 2009 *Science*

Purvis A. 2008. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 39:301–19

Tonini et al. 2016 *Biol Conservation*

Mishler et al. 2014 *Nature Comms*

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Effect of environmental changes on diversity, from fossil record

Pol and Leardi 2015 *PE-APA*

Lazarus et al. 2014 *PLoS ONE*

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Pinpoint taxa/groups at risk

AR Purvis A. 2008.
Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst. 39:301–19

Big animals...?

Forest et al. 2015 *Phil Trans R Soc B*

Arregoitia et al. 2013 *Proc R Soc B*

Older groups...?

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Pinpoint areas/species to prioritise

Areas or groups with high phylogenetic/evolutionary diversity

Tonini et al. 2016 *Biol Conservation*

Oliveira et al. 2016 *Glob Ecol Biogeog*

Mishler et al. 2014 *Nature Comms*

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Population genetics/distinctiveness

Population viability

Hybridisation

Before DNA: For 151 years these common North American birds were considered a single species, although differences in song and range were noted. Some bird species are indistinguishable by appearance

M. Stoeckle 2008

Cryptic species

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Fundamentally, *any* kind of statistical test across different taxa must take phylogeny into account, to avoid pseudoreplication

Silly example:

- 5/6 people in a house have a terrible disease,
- House statistically* has a „disease risk“!
- However, they may all be from the same family, and have inherited the disease!
- Phylogeny matters!

*well, the sample size is too small, but yeah

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

A real example:

Do bigger animals tend to go extinct more?

Cannot just do a normal T test, because maybe whales or elephants *in particular* tend to go extinct...

PHYLOGENY IN CONSERVATION

Do bigger animals tend to go extinct more?

...Do phylogenetic independent contrasts, to compare pairs of (bigger and smaller) taxa

...Or use phylogenetic regression, where you input tree etc.

 Purvis A. 2008.
Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst. 39:301–19

DRAWING PHYLOGENIES

Usually drawn as branching tree, to show hierarchy
Can be diagonal lines...

DRAWING PHYLOGENIES

Usually drawn as branching tree, to show hierarchy
Can be diagonal lines ...or parallel etc.

ANCESTORS

Tips = „real“ taxa

Nodes = hypothetical ancestors

BRIEF HISTORY OF LIFE

Where are we from? **Not just apes!**

BRIEF HISTORY OF LIFE

Where are we from? **Not just apes!**

Dipnoi

Lissamphibia

Amniota

BRIEF HISTORY OF LIFE

Where are we from? **Not just apes!**

BRIEF HISTORY OF LIFE

Where are we from? **Not just apes!**

BRIEF HISTORY OF LIFE

Where are we from? **Not just apes!**

CLASSIFICATION

Linnaean

Shared features

Hierarchy

Non-evolutionary

Carl von Linné (1707-1778)

Aves

Reptilia

CLASSIFICATION

Hennigian

Shared features

Branching tree

Evolutionary

Willi Hennig (1913-1976)

Archosauria

Reptilia

CLASSIFICATION

Even before Hennig, classification was increasingly evolutionary

R. Asher

CLASSIFICATION

Hennig

Only synapomorphy used for classification

Symplesiomorphy irrelevant

CLASSIFICATION

Phenetics

Overall similarity is relevant in grouping

No attempt to reconstruct evolutionary history

P. Sneath
(1923-2011)

CLASSIFICATION

Evolutionary taxonomy

Some kind of mixture of both!

E. Mayr (1904-2005)

Aves

Dinosauria

Crocodylia

Lepidosauria

AVES

REPTILIA

CLASSIFICATION

The debate is over, and **Hennigian taxonomy** is used today
We are all fish, chickens are dinosaurs.

CLASSIFICATION

Compare...

Non-phylogenetic

Phylogenetic Tree of Life

Phylogenetic

CLASSIFICATION

Important concepts ...only monophyletic groups now valid

Monophyletic group

Includes an ancestor
all of its descendants

CLADES

Paraphyletic group

Includes ancestor and
some, but not all of its
descendants

Polyphyletic group

Includes two convergent
descendants but not their
common ancestor

GRADES

Taxon A is highly **derived** and looks very
different from B, C, and ancestor of A,B,C

Taxon A and C share similar
traits through convergent
evolution

CLASSIFICATION

Monophyletic group

Includes ancestors and all descendents

Group is a true evolutionary lineage

CLASSIFICATION

Paraphyletic group

Includes *some* descendents and their common ancestor

Some descendents very „derived“, so excluded

CLASSIFICATION

Polyphyletic group

Includes some descendents but *not* their common ancestor

Convergent adaptations basis of grouping

CLASSIFICATION

Again, **only monophyletic groups are accepted in modern systematics** because only they represent a complete lineage

CLASSIFICATION

Other examples of paraphyly

Varanids

Snakes

Skinks

Gekkos

„Lizards“ is paraphyletic grade unless it includes snakes

CLASSIFICATION

Other examples of paraphyly

Dinosauria is a paraphyletic grade unless it includes birds

CLASSIFICATION

Other examples of paraphyly

„Foxes“ are a paraphyletic grade unless wolves, jackals, wild dogs etc. are also „foxes“

CLASSIFICATION

Other examples of polyphyly

Mosasaurus

Lizards/snakes

Ichthyosaurs

Plesiosaurs

Dinosaurs

„Marine reptiles“ are a polyphyletic grade if mosasaurs are included

CLASSIFICATION

Other examples of polyphyly

„Legless lizards“ developed several times separately

HOW DO WE INFER PHYLOGENIES?

WARNING: hard to follow without doing it!

Recommended:

Phylogenetics in Evolution and Ecology block course

10 days, mid-late September at Museum für Naturkunde
Accredited by university of Potsdam (6 credits)

Chance to try many different phylogenetic methods hands on

By Faysal Bibi, Johannes Müller, and (sometimes) me!

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HOW DO WE INFER PHYLOGENIES?

Data: morphology, molecules

Methods: parsimony, likelihood, Bayesian inference

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A) P(A)}{P(B)}$$

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

=Morphological features taxa are observed to share, e.g.

Hair

Feathers

Fingers

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Were the basis of Linnaean classification
E.g. petal number in flowers

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Continued to be basis of Hennigian taxonomy
Only **apomorphies**, not **plesiomorphies** count

Apomorphies are shared „derived“ characteristics of a group – innovations, not found in the ancestor of all taxa

Plesiomorphies are ancestral features, which are not helpful in identifying lineages

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Continued to be basis of Hennigian taxonomy
Only **apomorphies**, not **plesiomorphies** count

Fingers are a plesiomorphy, so not useful in grouping

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Continued to be basis of Hennigian taxonomy
Only **apomorphies**, not **plesiomorphies** count

Hair and feathers are apomorphies, so useful in grouping

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Important terminology

Apomorphy: a derived (=non-ancestral, new) feature

Autapomorphy: an apomorphy present in only a single taxon

Synapomorphy: a shared derived feature

Plesiomorphy: a retained ancestral feature

Symplesiomorphy: shared ancestral features

Homology: when similar features in different taxa have a common origin

Homoplasy: when similar features developed separately in different taxa

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Example

Homology: underlying forelimb structure (also homologous with your arms)

Homoplasy: presence of wings (developed separately in each group)

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Example

(Sym)plesiomorphy: forelimb in all tetrapods (useless in grouping)

(Syn)apomorphy: hand-wing in bats (groups bats to the exclusion of all other taxa)

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

How do we know what is a potential homologue?

It is always a guess, but...

Similar components

Similar relationship to other structures

Similar developmental pathways

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Homologues...

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Principle of parsimony

Tree which minimizes the number of changes (=most parsimonious) is preferred

„Occam's razor“

William of Ockham

Figure 18. The phylogenetic kinship relations between the species of a monophyletic group, represented in two different ways.

Entia non sunt multiplicanda praeter necessitatem

=More things should not be used than are necessary

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Principle of parsimony

Tree which minimizes the number of changes is preferred

„Occam's Ptolemy's razor“?

Figure 18. The phylogenetic kinship relations between the species of a monophyletic group, represented in two different ways.

William of Ockham

Ptolemy

Entia non sunt multiplicanda
“We consider it a good principle to explain the phenomena by the simplest hypothesis possible”
... use than are necessary

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

With few observations (=characters), phylogeny with fewest changes can be inferred by hand

Figure 18. The phylogenetic kinship relations between the species of a monophyletic group, represented in two different ways.

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Example

Left-hand tree preferred

One change

Two changes

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

With many observations, computers needed

Observations coded as matrix (characters x taxa) for analysis, with

characters and character states

If simple:

0 1

Feature: absent (0); present (1).

If more complicated, then:

Feature: absent (0); present and small (1); present and big (2).

0 1 2 etc.

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Example

Feathers: absent (0); present (1).

0

0

1

1

Forelimbs: big hands (0); small hands (1); wings (2).

0

1

1

2

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Matrix created

	Feathers: (0) absent; (1) present	Forelimbs: (0) large hands; (1) small hands; (2) wings
<i>Macropus</i>	0	0
<i>H. insapiens</i>	0	1
<i>Tyrannosaurus</i>	1	1
<i>Gallus</i>	1	2

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Features where all but one state is present for only one taxon (=are autapomorphies) usually excluded – parsimony uninformative

	Feathers: (0) absent; (1) present	Forelimbs: (0) large hands; (1) small hands; (2) wings
<i>Macropus</i>	0	0
<i>H. insapiens</i>	0	1
<i>Tyrannosaurus</i>	1	1
<i>Gallus</i>	1	2

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Real matrices much bigger...

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Narvaez et al. 2015 all taxa only binary characters.nex". The interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, Characters, Taxa&Trees, Analysis, View, Matrix, Alter, Select, Display, Analysis Matrix, Help) and a toolbar with various icons. The main area displays a "Character Matrix" with 103 taxa listed on the y-axis and 71 characters on the x-axis. The matrix cells contain binary data (0, 1, ?). The taxa listed include:

- 1 Bemisantis fagesti
- 2 Shomoosuchus djedect
- 3 Plectroisuchus omni
- 4 Pachyisuchus tibi
- 5 Lohecosuchus mega
- 6 Lohecosuchus mech
- 7 Alledapsuchus pree
- 8 Alledapsuchus subju
- 9 Arenysuchus gascaba
- 10 Acynodon ibereocitan
- 11 Acynodon adriaticus
- 12 Ihaetosuchus makad
- 13 Hylaeosaurus veebi
- 14 Borealosuchus threee
- 15 Borealosuchus formid
- 16 Borealosuchus wilsoni
- 17 Borealosuchus acutid
- 18 Borealosuchus stemb
- 19 Eothenacosaurus misi
- 20 Thoracosaurus neocer
- 21 Thoracosaurus macro
- 22 Eosuchus minor
- 23 Eosuchus leichei
- 24 Egagavialis africanus
- 25 Piscogavialis jugalipe
- 26 Gyposuchus colombi
- 27 Gavialis lewisi
- 28 Gavialis gangeticus
- 29 Boverisuchus vorax
- 30 Boverisuchus magnif
- 31 Planocrania bangdon
- 32 Planocrania datanger
- 33 Laldysuchus canad
- 34 Deinysuchus nigrand
- 35 Diplosynodon zateili
- 36 Diplosynodon hamton
- 37 Diplosynodon mueller
- 38 Diplosynodon formic
- 39 Diplosynodon deparisi

INFERRING PHYLOGENY: DATA

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Have **outgroup** outside group analysed to check which states are ancestral – no need to know this *a priori*

No feathers

No feathers

No feathers

Feathers

Feathers

Homo insapiens
plesiomorphic

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Parsimony analysis, finding tree with minimum number of character state changes, most common for morphology

PAUP*

TNT

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Try out coding...

The Cladisticules

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Try out coding...

	Head fused to thorax: (0) yes; (1) no.	Toes: (0) two; (1) one.	Legs: (0) four; (1) six.	Antennae: (0) absent; (1) present.	Horns: absent (0); present (1).	Thorax: (0) no pattern; (1) hour glass	Abdomen: (0) white; (1) black.
Joe*							
April							
Mike							
Tanya							
Bobby							
Jason							
Jerry							
Jane							

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

The Cladisticules

*outgroup

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Try out coding...

	Head fused to thorax: (0) yes; (1) no.	Toes: (0) two; (1) one.	Legs: (0) four; (1) six.	Antennae: (0) absent; (1) present.	Horns: absent (0); present (1).	Thorax: (0) no pattern; (1) hour glass	Abdomen: (0) white; (1) black.
Joe*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
April	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
Mike	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Tanya	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Bobby	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jason	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Jerry	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Jane	1	1	0	0	1	0	1

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

The Cladisticules

*outgroup

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

The tree would be...

Illustrating how to turn the nested proper subsets into a phylogenetic tree

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

The Cladisticules

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

The tree would be...

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

The Cladisticules

The final tree, with tic marks showing where evolutionary changes are inferred to have occurred. *Note character 7 (the homoplasy) is mapped to two branches.

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Consensus

All most parsimonious trees

Single consensus

Strict

Majority rule

Etc.

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Support values

Characters resampled: **bootstrap**

Taxa resampled: **jackknife**

Decay index: number of extra steps allowed above most parsimonious tree before node collapses

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Can upweight characters manually...

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Or on how well they fit initial tree, then repeat (implied weighting)...

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Issues with coding characters

Inapplicable or multistate?

Which?

Binary	Tail	1	1	0
	Red tail	1	0	–
	Blue tail	0	1	–
Multistate		0	1	2

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Issues with coding characters

Continuous variation

Where is the cutoff?

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Issues with coding characters

Continuous variation

Gap weighting

Gap coding

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

Issues with coding characters

Continuous variation

Phylogenetic morphometrics?

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DNA DATA

Most phylogenies for extant taxa use DNA

Generally more objective, easy to collect than morphology

Previously other molecules (e.g. proteins) used

Cannot be used for fossils ...although proteins might be able to be!

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DNA DATA

Similar principle to morphology

Homology between codon positions of sequence inferred
(alignment)

Each position „scored“ (automatically) depending which base at
that position

A	T	A	T	G	A	C
A	T	A	T	G	A	C
A	T	T	T	C	A	G
A	T	T	T	G	A	G

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Can be analysed using same parsimony algorithms as morphology

Each base position is a character, each base a state (**preferred**)

Can also code codons (i.e. three base pairs) as characters, and amino acids as states

Sp.1	ATATGAC	ATATGAC	Y Tyrosine
Sp.2	ATATGAC	ATATGAC	Y Tyrosine
Sp.3	ATTTGAG	ATTTGAG	F Phenylalanine
Sp.4	ATTTGAG	ATTTGAG	F Phenylalanine

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DNA DATA

Often trees from DNA resolve new groups, and disagree with morphology

DNA mostly correct! (will explain)

...Whales

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DNA DATA

Where are whales from?

Fossils seemed to indicate mesonychids

DNA indicated artiodactyls....

Mesonychid

Artiodactyls

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Before

After

Artiodactyla

Cetartiodactyla

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DNA DATA

- Site 142 is plesiomorphic (uninformative)
- Site 192 is an autapomorphic (uninformative)
- Sites 162, 166 & 177 are synapomorphies (informative)

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Sites 162, 166 conflict with 177 - homoplasy

What is the most parsimonious tree of all characters?

Whales early – 47 changes

Whales late (Whippomorpha!) – 41 changes

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Now backed up by fossils! Navicular trochlea etc.

Artiocetus clavis

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DNA DATA

Many examples where DNA finds a different topology, later backed up by new morphological data

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Major mammal clades

Parallel adaptive radiations in two major clades of placental mammals

Ole Madsen^{††}, Mark Scally^{†‡§}, Christophe J. Douady^{†§}, Diana J. Kao[‡],
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Higher level relationships among placental
mammals inferred from nuclear DNA. Here we
compare relationships inferred from length

Endemic African mammals shake the phylogenetic tree

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The order Insectivora, including living taxa (lipotyphlans) and
archaic fossil forms, is central to the question of higher-level
relationships among placental mammals¹. Beginning with
Huxley², it has been argued that insectivores retain many primi-
tive features and are closer to the ancestral stock of mammals than
are other living groups³. Nevertheless, cladistic analysis suggests
that living insectivores, at least, are united by derived anatomical
features⁴. Here we analyse DNA sequences from three mito-
chondrial genes and two nuclear genes to examine relationships
of insectivores to other mammals. The representative insectivore
are not monophyletic in any of our analyses. Relationships
elephant shrews and a presumed African insectivore are sister to
presumed African insectivores.

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Major mammal clades

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Major mammal clades

Morphological
apomorphies identified

BMC Biology

Research article

Dental eruption in afrotherian mammals
Robert J Asher*¹ and Thomas Lehmann²

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DNA DATA

Grebes and divers

Two additional synapomorphies of grebes Podicipedidae and flamingos Phoenicopteridae

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Manegold A. 2006. Two additional synapomorphies of grebes Podicipedidae and flamingos Phoenicopteridae. Acta Ornithol. 41: 79-82.

Abstract. Sister group relationship of grebes and flamingos is well supported by both molecular and morphological data. Surprisingly, most of the morphological characters now recognized as synapomorphies of grebes and flamingos have long been known in both taxa, but they were never considered to be homologous. The same is true of two additional synapomorphies discussed here: the presence of nail-like ungual phalanges and prominent caudolateral projections on the ventral side of the cervical vertebrae. †Palaeodidae, morphology, phylogeny

2006, accepted — April 2006

...morphies for this mono-
...characters now rec-
...the presence
...Piscarpus

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DNA DATA

Birds

...and no real morphological evidence

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Why is DNA better?

More data

Better analysis (will explain)

DNA fits biogeography

Problems affect morphology:

- Convergence
- Extreme/rapid divergence

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DNA DATA

Substitution rates differ (transitions more common than transversions)

Can weight steps in parsimony to simulate this

Transitions:

Transversions:

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DNA DATA

Can also use model based, **likelihood** approaches

Likelihood calculates the probability of the data on a particular tree and incorporating the likelihood of each state change

That is, the probability of the data (sequences) given the hypothesis (tree and model of evolution)

ATATGAC
ATATGAC
ATTCAG
ATTTGAG

Coin example:

You have heads (data). Assuming a fair coin (hypothesis), the chance of getting heads is $\frac{1}{2}$.

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Most likely tree(s) chosen. Support values are likelihood of node (e.g. 0.5)

Basic Jukes-Cantor model, no difference between substitutions:

	A	G	C	T
A	-3α	α	α	α
G	α	-3α	α	α
C	α	α	-3α	α
T	α	α	α	-3α

α = substitution rate

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DNA DATA

Augmented models, with difference between substitutions:

Figure 1 | **Markov models of nucleotide substitution.** The thickness of the arrows indicates the substitution rates of the four nucleotides (T, C, A and G), and the sizes of the circles represent the nucleotide frequencies when the substitution process is in equilibrium. Note that both JC69 and K80 predict equal proportions of the four nucleotides.

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DNA DATA

Can create very complex models...

The best model can be chosen by AIC, which balances fit against parameters

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DNA DATA

But what about the probability of the hypothesis itself?

This is where **Bayesian probability** comes in. Until relatively recently too computationally expensive, but arguably better.

Bayes theorem:

This is conventional likelihood

$$P(H|D) = P(H) * P(D|H) / P(D)$$

Coin example:

You have heads (data). The probability you have a fair coin is:

probability a fair coin exists * probability of heads given a fair coin / probability heads exists

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Bayes theorem:

$$P(H|D) = P(H) * P(D|H) / P(D)$$

Another example

Pregnancy test...

The test is positive!

The chance of a positive result (D) is 0.99 if pregnant (H), i.e. $P(D|H)$ – “99% accuracy”!

...But with Bayesian probability you must also include:

- (i) the probability of getting a positive result full stop (including false positives), i.e. $P(D)$
- (ii) the probability of pregnancy in the wider population, i.e. $P(H)$

Say these are 0.5 and 0.1, then:

$$0.1 * 0.99 / 0.5 = 0.198$$

...phew!? Maybe just beer...

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) computational methods have allowed tractable Bayesian phylogenetic inference

This consists of independent search chains which “step” through the data “landscape”, reducing the computational load

Illustration of MCMC method process (Lewis, 2011)

Sometimes stuck on peaks in “low valleys” – Metropolis coupled MCMC to solve this

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Once chains converge, the trees are looking good – “burn in” until chains converge

Trace of posterior prob. in Tracer

<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/tracer/>

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

DNA DATA

Markov (Mk) model used in Bayesian – can include rate heterogeneity across sites (Γ)

Large tree sample output

Posterior probabilities at nodes show support (e.g. 0.5)

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

TYPICAL SOFTWARE

Maximum likelihood: RaxML; PhyLip

Bayesian: MrBayes; RevBayes; BEAST

RAXML

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)}$$

Mr Bayes
Bayesian Inference
of Phylogeny

RevBayes
Bayesian phylogenetic
language

BEAST
Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis Sampling Trees

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL DATA

Which method best?

Even more debatable!

We don't know the right model for morphology (is there one model?!)

Usually use simply Lewis Mk

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL DATA

Which method best?

Some evidence Bayesian better, but maybe due to lower (incl. false) resolution, and fit to stratigraphy worse...

BIOLOGY LETTERS
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Palaeontology

Bayesian methods outperform parsimony but at the expense of precision in the estimation of phylogeny from discrete morphological data

Joseph E. O'Reilly^{1,†}, Mark N. Puttick^{1,†}, Luke Parry¹, Alastair R. T. James E. Tarver¹, James Fleming¹, Davide Pisani^{1,2} and Philip C. J. Donoghue^{1,3}

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Research

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2016.0081>

Received: 28 January 2016
Accepted: 21 March 2016

Subject Areas:
palaeontology, taxonomy and systematics, evolution

Keywords:
parsimony, Bayesian, likelihood, phylogenetics, morphology

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Different analytical methods can yield competing phylogenetic hypotheses. However, the history of reconstruction using morphological data is not Bayesian analysis, recovers more stratigraphically congruent phylogenetic trees.

Received: 12 April 2018
Accepted: 19 May 2018

Subject Areas:
palaeontology, taxonomy and systematics, evolution

Keywords:
morphology, phylogeny, parsimony, stratigraphic congruence

BIOLOGY LETTERS
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Palaeontology

Parsimony, not Bayesian analysis, recovers more stratigraphically congruent phylogenetic trees

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Reconstructing evolutionary histories requires accurate phylogenetic trees. Recent simulation studies suggest that probabilistic phylogenetic methods using morphological data are more accurate than traditional parsimony. Here, we use empirical data to compare Bayesian and parsimony methods in terms of their congruence with the distribution of fossil tetrapods finds that Bayesian independent stratigraphic congruence than the parsimony analyses are more accurate. The distribution of fossil tetrapods from historical data as an independent test of stratigraphic congruence.

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL DATA

Which method best?

Continued subject of research

Can we get better models for morphology, better priors (e.g. proportion variable sites)?

Models for different regions?

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL DATA

Character-free methods

Phylogenetic morphometrics

Overall similarity from 3D shapes (but phenetic)

Likelihood/Bayesian continuous data? Future, but still computationally expensive

RevBayes
Bayesian phylogenetic language

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL/DNA DATA

“Phenetic” methods still usable

Especially neighbour joining

Can give reasonable, heuristic network or tree

Especially useful if much hybridization

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

PROTEIN DATA

Proteins largely abandoned for living taxa

Influenced by selection, and less info than DNA

But seems they may be able to be sequenced from fossils!

Can use any method, but Bayesian or likelihood preferred

RevBayes
Bayesian phylogenetic
language

 SplitsTree4

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

MORPHOLOGICAL/DNA DATA

Explicitly including hybridization/introgression

Woolly mammoths

Columbian mammoth

Asian elephants

Forest elephant

Savanna elephant

American mastodons

Palkopoulou et al.

USING PHYLOGENY

TIME TREES

Node-based fossil calibrations

Molecular clock

Estimate origination time of all lineages

Meredith et al. 2011 Science

USING PHYLOGENY

TIME TREES

Tip-based calibrations with fossils as tips

USING PHYLOGENY

TIME TREES

Fossil (morphology) only:

tip dating with minimum branch lengths, or lengths linked to morphology

USING PHYLOGENY

TIME TREES

Mammal radiation

O'Leary et al. 2013 Science

Meredith et al. 2011 Science

FIGURE 1. The timing of placental mammal evolution.

USING/INFERRING PHYLOGENY

TIME TREES

Can affect relationships, if stratigraphy included

Lee & Yates 2018, Proc B

PROCEEDINGS B
rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org

Research

Cite this article: Lee MSY, Yates AM. 2018 Tip-dating and homoplasy: reconciling the shallow molecular divergences of modern gharials with their long fossil record. *Proc. R. Soc. B* 285: 20181071. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.1071>

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Accepted: 30 May 2018

Tip-dating and homoplasy: reconciling the shallow molecular divergences of modern gharials with their long fossil record

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Simultaneously analysing morphological, molecular and stratigraphic data suggests a potential resolution to a major remaining inconsistency in crocodylian evolution. The ancient, long-snouted thoracosauroids have always been placed near the Indian gharial *Gavialis*, but their antiquity (ca 72 Ma) is highly incongruous with genomic evidence for the young age of the *Gavialis* lineage (ca 40 Ma). We reconcile this contradiction with an updated morphological dataset and novel analysis, and demonstrate that thoracosauroids and gharials. The extensive similarities between thoracosauroids and gharials shown to be an almost 'perfect storm' of homoplasy, combining adaptations to fish-eating, as well as resemblances between genomic traits (thoracosauroids) and atavisms (*Gavialis*). Phylogenetic ignore stratigraphy (parsimony) and undated Bayesian methods to tease apart these similarities and invariably unite thoracosauroids. However, tip-dated Bayesian approaches additionally account for the temporal gap separating ancient (thoracosauroids) and modern (gharials) lineages of similar long-snouted crocodylians, favouring a phylogeny which places thoracosauroids

INFERRING PHYLOGENY

TYPICAL TIME TREE

SOFTWARE

Bayesian: BEAST; BEAUTi

Parsimony: various R packages

BEAST

Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis Sampling Trees

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

As mentioned at start, there are LOADS of applications!

For any study looking at several species (and often those looking at one!), phylogeny must be considered

Mishler et al. 2014 *Nature Comms*

Tonini et al. 2016 *Biol Conservation*

Purvis A. 2008.
Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst. 39:301–19

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

Phylogenetic diversity

More and more considered when conserving specific areas, e.g.:

- Australia for example has very different animals (distantly related) compared to everywhere else, so needs preserving!
- The tuatara is the last remnant of a huge clade of reptiles, and so is very evolutionary unique - worth conserving?

Oliveira et al. 2016 *Glob Ecol Biogeog*

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

Cryptic species

Increasingly recognized to exist, using molecular phylogenetics

- E.g. dwarf crocodiles – actually three species
- Need to prioritise conservation in different areas, to preserve genetic diversity

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

Checking which kinds of taxa are most at risk

Looking at traits which may endanger them

e.g. body size, reproduction rate, generalists v. specialists

Use a method which takes into account phylogeny

- Phylogenetic independent contrasts
- Phylogenetic generalized least squares (PGLS)
- Phylogenetic generalized linear mixed models (PGLMM)

Ives and Helmus 2011 *Ecol Monographs*

Purvis A. 2008.

Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst. 39:301–19

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

Any other correlation

Always think phylogenetically when you do a study!!

E.g. if the detectability of birds, which affects their counts by conservationists

<https://vimeo.com/291323964>

USING PHYLOGENY

CONSERVATION

Looking at how extinctions/climate change have impacted biodiversity

Can help us predict the effects of future extinction events

E.g. corals during warm intervals

Time series correlations (GLS)

Mihaljević et al. 2017 *Paleobiology*

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

COEVOLUTION

Cospeciation
Congruent

Host jumping

Duplication “Missing the boat”

Incongruent

Figs

Wasps

Phylogenetic reconciliation analysis

Tests if two phylogenies more different than expected by chance

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

COEVOLUTION

Very high
pollinator
specificity

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

RATES OF CHANGE

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

TRENDS THROUGH TIME

Sookias et al. 2012 *Proc R Soc B*

Sookias et al. 2012 *Biol Lett*

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

CONVERGENT EVOLUTION

USING PHYLOGENY – EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY

ANCESTRAL STATES/DIRECTION OF CHANGE

Jansa et al. 2014 *Evolution*

Fröbisch et al. 2015 *Nature*

USING PHYLOGENY

HOW?

Host of different software

- BAMM, BayesTraits – rates
- Mesquite for ancestral states

Various different R packages

- Geiger - evolutionary trends
- RRPhylo – evolutionary rates
- Packages for PGLS, independent contrasts

Google your question, and you'll probably find what you need! (or ask me!)

Also recommend (of course!) **Phylogenetics in Ecology and Evolution** block course, and Physalia courses (but expensive – only if can get price covered! <https://www.physalia-courses.org/courses-workshops/course44/>)

USING PHYLOGENY – WIDER USES

LINGUISTICS

GERMANIC

INDO-EUROPEAN

	water	house
German	Wasser	Haus
English	water	house
French	eau	maison
Russian	voda	dom

	water	house
German	0	0
English	0	0
French	1	1
Russian	0	2

USING PHYLOGENY – WIDER USES

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

Network/hybridization especially relevant

Can use phonetic and other continuous data

ANY QUESTIONS?

Now or later, just ask or get in touch...

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für Natur
MUSEUM FÜR
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Conservation-related further reading

- Purvis, A. (2008). Phylogenetic Approaches to the Study of Extinction. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 39(1), 301-319
<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/full/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-063008-102010>
- Rolland, J et al. (2012). Using phylogenies in conservation: new perspectives. *Biology Letters*, 8(5), 692-694. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/full/10.1098/rsbl.2011.1024>
- Arregoitia, L. D. V et al. (2013). Phylogenetic correlates of extinction risk in mammals: species in older lineages are not at greater risk. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 280(1765), 20131092. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/full/10.1098/rspb.2013.1092>
- Forest, F. et al. (2015). Phylogeny, extinction and conservation: embracing uncertainties in a time of urgency. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 370(1662), 20140002. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/full/10.1098/rstb.2014.0002>
- Fernández-García, José Luis. "Phylogenetics for Wildlife Conservation." *Phylogenetics* (2017): 27. <https://www.intechopen.com/books/phylogenetics/phylogenetics-for-wildlife-conservation>
- Vézquez, D. P., & Gittleman, J. L. (1998). Biodiversity conservation: Does phylogeny matter? *Current Biology*, 8(11), R379-R381. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960982298702428>
- Forest, F. et al. (2007). Preserving the evolutionary potential of floras in biodiversity hotspots. *Nature*, 445(7129), 757-760. <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature05587>

Just email me if you can't get hold of these. There is also something called sci-hub...